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THE GEOTECHNICAL ASPECTS OF THE DEEP BASEMENT FOR THE JERVIS STREET SHOPPING CENTRE

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SYNOPSIS

This paper discusses the design and construction of the deep basement for the recently completed Jervis Street Shopping Centre in Dublin. The Centre provides a total of 42 retail units in addition to 750 car parking spaces. The overall cost of the project is estimated to be £100m. The basement of the Centre involved an excavation of up to 7m depth adjacent to some sensitive structures such as the facade of the former Jervis St. Hospital and the existing Marks and Spencer Store. The paper is concerned with aspects relating to the basement only and not to the general planning issues or the design and construction of the building itself.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The Jervis St. Shopping Centre was constructed between July 1995 and November 1996 by Piers Contracting Ltd. (PCL) for their client Stamshaw Ltd. Design and Management Ltd. (D & M) were Project Managers, Architect and Civil and Structural Engineer for the project. D & M required that the secant piling and rock anchorage contracts to be let on a design and construct basis. As a result of this Ove Arup and Partners Ireland (OAPI) were appointed by Murphy International Ltd. and Rocklift Ltd. to assist them in the design issues relating to the secant pile retaining wall and the rock anchorages respectively. OAPI were also appointed by PCL to advise them on some temporary works issues during the development.

2.0 THE SITE

2.1 Location and Topography

The site, which occupies an area of some 0.9ha, was formerly occupied by the Jervis St. Hospital. It is bounded to the north by Mary St., to the west by Jervis St., to the south by Upper Abbey St. and to the east by the existing Marks and Spencer Store. The site location is shown on Figure 1. The site is located approximately 250m north of the River Liffey.

The hospital buildings towards the centre of the site were demolished to street level in the late 1980's leaving a generally flat area, at an elevation of about +3.5mOD, which was then used for car parking.

FIGURE 1 SITE LOCATION

2.2 History

The site area remained undeveloped until relatively recent times. Development of the area commenced in 1677, in conjunction with the construction of Ormond Quay and Bachelor's Walk. The developer, Sir Humphrey Jervis, constructed a street system on the lands of St. Mary's Abbey and the area became a fashionable residential quarter.

No. 14 Jervis St., later to become Jervis St. Hospital, was originally the home of The Earl of Charlemont. The Earl moved to what is now the Hugh Lane Gallery in Parnell Square in 1786 and No. 14 was occupied by the Dublin Charitable Infirmary.

In 1853 the Sisters of Mercy took over the running of the nursing duties of the hospital. The quality of the medical care improved and the hospital expanded. The building was rebuilt in 1886 and the training school for nurses along Mary St. was added in 1891.

The hospital was closed in 1987 with the opening of Beaumont Hospital. Most of the buildings were demolished to ground level in the late 1980's to make space for car parking. The remaining structures, with the exception of the facades on Jervis St. and Mary St. and Nos. 124 and 125 Upper Abbey St. were demolished in 1995, just prior to construction work on the shopping centre.

Nos. 124 and 125 Upper Abbey St., which were both built about 1760, were considered to be of "national importance" by the Dublin Civic Trust and were thus incorporated into the development.

2.3 Geology from Site Investigation

Two site investigations were carried out prior to the development by Site Investigations Ltd. under the directions of D & M. The first investigation comprised nine shell and auger boreholes, five of which were extended by rotary coring, together with some laboratory testing. The second investigation involved the construction of a pumping well together with two observation holes. The ground conditions revealed by these investigations are summarised in Table 1.

Table 1: Ground Conditions from Site Investigations

Stratum	Thickness (m)
-	Range / Average
Made Ground	2.6 - 2.7 / 3.2
Alluvium	0.0 - 0.6 / 0.1
Gravels	1.7 - 3.0 / 2.2
Black Boulder Clay	0.0 - 1.6 / 0.8
Weathered Rock	0.1 - 1.9 / 0.5
Intact Rock	7.5 proven

The most important materials as far as the basement construction was concerned were the made ground, the gravels and the rock and these are described in more detail as follows:

The made ground was a variable mixture of brick, masonry, steel, timber etc. in a silty clay matrix. The material included large pieces of steel and heavily reinforced concrete which remained from former hospital basement structures.

The gravels comprised a medium dense to dense fine to coarse sandy gravel.

The rock is a fine grained slightly weathered limestone interbedded with zones of black very fine grained severely weathered limestone. The weathered rock generally had the appearance either of blocks of limestone surrounded both vertically and horizontally with bands of black silty clay or of cobbles and boulders of limestone in a matrix of silty clay.

Groundwater was generally encountered 3.0m to 3.5m below ground level at an elevation of 0.0mOD to 0.5mOD.

A geological section through the site is shown on Figure 2.

3.0 Proposed Development

The maximum basement depth evolved from the need to provide a clear span for large articulated lorries making deliveries underground to the service yard area. It was found that the resulting level of the loading bay would provide good retail space if applied to the remainder of the basement area. Hence, a two level basement scheme was developed.

The purpose of the basement then is both to allow all deliveries to the store from below street level and to provide for some retail space. The basement structure is therefore

FIGURE 2 - GEOLOGY/CROSS SECTION THROUGH BUILDING

of necessity designed to be completely waterproof (Grade 4).

The basement dig depth around the perimeter of the site varied between about 5.5m along Upper Abbey Street to about 7.25m along the Mary St. side of the site, see Figure 2. The maximum dig depth for foundations was about 9.7m below ground level, which was about 6.5m below the water table. It is important to note that the excavation involved removal of rock material over a large part of the site.

Several sensitive structures are located adjacent to the site and therefore the ground movements associated with the construction of the basement had to be minimised so as to prevent any damage to these structures. The sensitive structures are as follows:

1. Jervis St. Hospital Facade,
2. Marks and Spencer Store,
3. Quinnsworth Facade on Mary St.,
4. Listed Buildings on Upper Abbey St.
5. Keating's Public House,

Structural columns are located on or adjacent to the edge of the structure, therefore the retaining wall had to be designed to resist vertical structural loads of up to 2150 kN/m run as well as the

horizontal loading due to soil, water and building surcharge.

4.0 Choice of Basement Structure

4.1 General

It became clear from an early stage that because of the adjacent sensitive structures, it would not be possible to construct the basement, over the whole site area, using conventional reinforced concrete in an open cut. It was decided that the only feasible solutions were either:

1. Reduce the basement size to encompass the centre of the site only,
2. Construction within a temporary sheet piled wall or,
3. A permanent secant piled wall.

An economic assessment was carried out and it was found that the cost of losing 0.3m width of space around the perimeter of the site, over a 10 year period, was approximately £0.26m. Option one was therefore ruled out.

The secant pile solution was technically more attractive than the sheet pile one as it was stiffer, stronger, more water resistant and could support the structural loading.

However, as the sheet piled solution was estimated to be up to £0.5m cheaper it was decided to carry out a sheet piling trial.

4.2 Sheet Pile Trial

The trial involved the construction of a sheet pile cofferdam of approximate dimensions 5m x 5m by 5.5m deep, using Larssen 25W sheet piles. The trial was carried out by Murphy International Ltd.

The first difficulty encountered was that it proved impossible to drive the sheet piles through the fill material due to the presence of obstructions in the form of large pieces of concrete, steel and masonry. Work was delayed while the material was removed by a combination of excavation using a large mechanical excavator and by thermal cutting of the steel.

Once the obstructions had been removed the sheet piles were driven with an ICE223 vibratory hammer to "refusal" at the top of the weathered rock / bedrock. This hammer has an applied eccentric moment of 11.5kNm.

Excavation then proceeded. It was noticed that the volume of water flowing into the

excavation was significant. It became apparent that this large volume was due to the inability to create an adequate seal at interface of the sheet piles and the weathered rock due to the occurrence of blocks of rock in stepped ledges. Water was flowing into the excavation from beneath the piles.

The initial concerns of noise and vibration proved to be unfounded. Maximum vibration levels of 0.6 mm/s and 2.6 mm/s were recorded on the Marks and Spencer wall, 10m from the piling operations, during piling and breaking out rubble respectively. Noise levels were also low.

A large inflow of water could possibly be controlled by a significant degree of pumping. However, the inflow would be accompanied by a loss of ground outside the piles. Because of these difficulties and the potential consequences from the adjacent buildings, it was decided to adopt the secant pile wall solution.

5.0 Secant Pile Wall Design

5.1 Design Methodology

The design involved the following steps:

1. Determine the pile toe-in required to support the structural loads,
2. Check that this toe-in was adequate to prevent significant water flow into the excavation,
3. Check the lateral stability of the wall using the computer program STAWAL,
4. Calculate the bending moments, shear forces, prop forces and wall deflections using the computer program FREW.

Structural Loads

This calculation was performed using conventional static type hand calculations assuming the piles were obtaining support from the intact rock only and that the ultimate skin friction and end bearing values were 2500 kN/m² and 6000 - 10,000 kN / m² respectively.

STAWAL

The program STAWAL was developed by OASYS (software group in Arup). It performs calculations using conventional Rankine active and passive earth pressure theory.

FREW

As the FREW calculations were the most

important of those carried out, it is worth dwelling a little on the details of the program. In FREW, which is also an OASYS program, the soil is modeled as an elastic - plastic solid.

The soil stiffness matrices are developed from prestored finite element stiffness matrices which are scaled to the parameters of the given problem. Beginning from the in-situ at rest pressures, the program analyses the behaviour for each stage of the construction sequence and limits the soil stresses to within the active or passive limits.

Allowance is made for arching within the soil body. Full details of the assumptions made in the analysis method are given in Pappin et al. (1986, Ref. 1).

FREW has been proven to give reliable results in a variety of ground conditions, including weak rocks, see for example Curtis and Mirzabaigian (1992, Ref. 2) and Wallace, et.al. (1992, Ref. 3)

5.2 Pile Size and Configuration

The chosen pile size and configuration is shown on Figure 3. The wall comprises of interlocking male and female piles. The piles are 900mm dia. through the overburden, reducing to 810mm dia. in the rock. A 900mm dia. pile solution was chosen as it was much quicker to build than the 600mm dia. one, which was the alternative solution. Also it was not clear

whether the 600mm dia. piles could support the lateral loads and vertical structural loads. The overlap between the 900mm dia. piles is 130mm resulting in a centre to centre distance between the male piles of 1.54m. This detail is similar to that used elsewhere for example Sherwood et. al. (1989, Ref. 4.)

The male piles were constructed using C35N concrete and reinforced with 8 No. T32 reinforcing bars. The female piles were constructed of C7N concrete and were unreinforced. They were designed to have a toe level of at least 0.5m below the proposed excavation level to ensure an adequate water cut-off.

The male piles needed a greater toe-in for structural reasons, which will be discussed below.

5.3 Soil Parameters

The soil parameter used in the design are given below on Table 2. They are based on the results of the site investigation, published data from other sites in Dublin (e.g. Farrell & Wall, 1990, Ref. 5 and Farrell et al., 1995, Ref. 6) and on OAPI experience.

The FREW analysis is most sensitive to the choices of the values of E_h and K_o .

Table 2: Soil Parameters

Material	E_h (kN / m ²)	γ (kN / m ³)	K_o	ϕ^1	c (kN/ m ²)	SPT 'N'
Made Ground	30,000	18	0.5	30	0	13
Alluvium	5,000	17	1.0	(28*)	20	-
Gravels	35,000	20	1.0	30	0	21
Black Boulder Clay	100,000	20	1.3	(36*)	270	45
Weathered Rock	100,000	22	1.0	45	0	-
Intact Rock	300,000	24	1.0	-	6000	-

* effective stress parameter used in STAWAL analysis.

5.4 Wall Parameters

The wall parameters required in the analysis were simply the toe level and the stiffness, EI.

5.5 Prop Parameters

Experience indicates that when a cantilever height exceeds about 4.5m, it is necessary to prop a retaining wall with one or more levels of support. This was particularly true in the case of Jervis St. due to the adjacent sensitive structures. The prop parameters required for the analysis were its inclination and stiffness, EA/L.

5.6 Surcharge Loading

The surcharge loading was applied by assuming the adjacent foundations acted as a distributed load of width equal to the width of the foundation. The surcharge loads were high and had a significant effect on the analyses. For example the loading due to the Jervis St. Facade and Marks and Spencer were 460 kN / m² and 500 kN / m² respectively.

6.0 Design Implications - Secant Wall

6.1 Pile Embedment

The most severe vertical load to be imposed is 3,300kN per male pile. Based on the parameters mentioned earlier a rock socket length of 0.88 m was calculated. To allow for such eventualities as over dig or even the rock becoming loosened during construction, it was decided to increase the depth of embedment to 1.5m in the heavily loaded areas (e.g. Marks and Spencer). In other areas (e.g. Abbey Street boundary)

the imposed vertical loading is significantly less at around 1155 kN per male pile. These loads can be accommodated in end bearing only and so a reduced depth of embedment was adopted.

An analysis was subsequently carried out to investigate the depth of embedment required to provide overall stability with full excavation and surcharge loading included. This analysis was carried out with the computer programme STAWAL using adequately factored effective stress soil parameters. The analysis concluded that only a minimal embedment into sound rock was required to provide sufficient toe reaction.

Therefore, in areas where the imposed vertical loading is high or sensitive structures are located adjacent to the wall, the minimum depth of embedment was set at 1.5m into intact bedrock. In areas where the vertical loading is significantly lower and only pavements are located next to the wall the minimum depth of embedment was set at 0.75m.

6.2 Pile Reinforcing

As discussed the computer program FREW was used to model the wall system in service. The FREW model is set up so as to represent the various construction stages carried out on site. The construction stages used in this case were:

- Stage 0: Set up the problem.
- Stage 1: Apply the surcharge loading, excavate leaving a berm.
- Stage 2: Install temporary props, excavate to formation.
- Stage 3: Install permanent props (floor slabs), remove the temporary props.

A total of eight design cases were analysed to model the various surcharge conditions

and excavation depths around the perimeter of the site.

FREW outputs values of wall bending moments and shear forces. An example of the graphical output from FREW is presented in Figures 4A and 4B.

Calculated wall bending moments were between 170 kNm/m and 370 kNm/m. The maximum ultimate pile bending moment was thus 855 kNm (BM x 1.5 FoS x 1.54 c/c). It was decided that the piles should contain a minimum of 1% steel by area. This equated to 6,362 mm² of steel or 8 No. T32. It was found that 1% reinforcement requirement was sufficient for all cases calculated.

6.3 Prop Forces

The prop forces were also determined using FREW. The temporary prop details were designed by the groundwork and demolition contractor's (Sean Hegarty Demolition Limited) consultant engineer Barrett-Mahony Limited, (BML). OAPI and BML co-operated to ensure that the prop parameters used by both firms were compatible.

The temporary prop forces calculated by FREW were between 100 kN/m and 185 kN/m (service).

BML decided to employ universal column (UC) sections at 6m c/c as the main temporary prop element. The UC sections used were 254 x 254 x 73 kg/m and 305 x 305 x 97 kg/m. No bracing of the props was required.

A typical temporary prop detail is shown on Figure 5.

In the permanent condition the ground floor slab is employed as the permanent prop.

The prop stiffness and geometry were changed in FREW to model the action of the floor slabs and the permanent prop forces determined. These forces calculated varied between 85 kN/m and 115 kN/m. These forces were then reported to D&M to ensure that they could be accommodated.

6.4 Wall Displacements

The predicted maximum wall displacements at the top of the piles varied between 7.0 mm where the wall is surcharged only by Abbey Street and where the maximum excavation depth was approximately 6.25 mm and 17.0 mm where the wall was loaded by the Marks & Spencer building's foundation and the depth of excavation was approximately 7.25 m.

These predictions were considered to be upperbound values. It was an insurance stipulation that the maximum movement at mid height of the secant pile wall (approx. level of foundations of adjacent buildings) should not exceed 12mm. This value was not exceeded in any of the analyses.

6.5 Ground Movements

As FREW is only able to determine lateral retaining wall movements and not the associated ground movements, these were predicted using the rule of thumb experience based methods which are used in the U.S. (Clough and O'Rourke, 1990, Ref. 6 and Clough et. al., 1989, Ref. 7).

For the Marks and Spencer area it was calculated that the maximum lateral wall movement of 17mm at ground level would be accompanied by a maximum vertical ground movement of 12mm and this would reduce to zero 15m from the retaining wall, see Figure 6. The corresponding maximum vertical movement at the level of the Marks and Spencer foundation was 3mm to 4mm, see Figure 6. Again it was an insurance stipulation that these values should not be exceeded.

7.0 Permanent Works Design

7.1 Basement Slab

The basement slab was initially intended to be a flat slab type construction for a single level basement. However the evolution of the split level basement, due to the deep service yard, meant that an uneconomic flat slab of overall thickness 1.1m would have been required to resist the uplift loading.

FIGURE 4A - FREW OUTPUT EARTH PRESSURES

FIGURE 4B - FREW OUTPUT BENDING MOMENT & DISPLACEMENT

Where there is a regular grid of pads at reasonable centres, the chosen solution comprised conventional pads with the basement slab spanning one way between pads. A typical detail is shown on Figure 7. This solution meant that that pumping had to be maintained until a dead load comprising 5 stories of the building was in place. This solution resulted in a saving of some £0.5m.

In areas which are substantially column free the slab is designed as a flat slab spanning between rock anchorages at approx. 2.5m centres.

7.2 Pad Footings

The pad footings were designed to bear on the weathered rock with an allowable bearing pressure of 500 kN/m².

7.3 Retaining Wall

In order to provide a Grade 4 waterproofed environment, a reinforced concrete retaining wall was constructed inside the secant pile wall, see Figure 8. It was designed to span horizontally between male piles at 1.54m centres. In the vertical direction the wall is pinned to the male piles at 0.9m centres with steel L bars. This resulted in an economical wall thickness of only 150mm.

7.4 Waterproofing

In addition to the reinforced concrete wall described above a Delta ("egg box") cavity drain was installed between the concrete wall and the internal masonry wall. A Delta drain was also installed on top of slabs and pads with water bars at all joints.

A detail of the retaining wall / slab junction is shown on Figure 9.

Of particular concern was the detail at the rock anchorage head. Lack of attention to detail has led to some problems in other structures in the past. The final detail adopted is shown on Figure 10.

8.0 Construction

8.1 Piling

The piles were formed using a bored cast-in-situ method. A total of approximately 300 male and 300 female piles were

FIGURE 5 - PROP DETAIL

FIGURE 6 - PREDICTED GROUND MOVEMENT

constructed by the piling contractor Murphy International Ltd. The pile lengths varied between 6.5m and 11.9m. The value of the piling contract was approximately £1m.

Excavation was initially carried out along the line of the secant pile wall in order to remove obstructions. As the on-plan position of the secant piles is important, each pile was located using a guide frame. A 900 mm dia. open ended steel casing was then rotated into the ground and the overburden materials removed using a Soilmec R10 boring rig fitted with a 900 mm diameter auger. The procedure of advancing the casing and augering the soils continued until the casing reached the surface of the rock and all of the overburden was removed from inside the casing.

The rock was removed to the required depth in a unlined hole. A rotary percussive Ingersoll-Rand cluster drill comprising five 250mm diameter drill bits mounted on a Soilmec RT3 rotating shaft and carried by a 40T Hitachi crane was used for this purpose. The overall diameter of the rock socket formed was 810 mm.

The reinforcement cages were placed in the male piles and the piles were concreted using a tremie pipe. The temporary casing was then removed. The sequence of construction of the piles was generally as follows:

- bore and concrete every second female pile constructing four in total;
- 24 hours after the concrete has been placed, bore and concrete the intermediate female piles and leave the concrete set for a further 24 hours;
- form the male piles, which interlock with the female piles, in the same sequence as above.

Work was carried out only on every second pile at any one time to minimise disturbance to the fresh concrete.

8.2 Piling Problems

Some problems that were encountered during the piling works were as follows:

Space

The general busy nature of the site sometimes made access for piling rigs difficult. It is important that the piling works are carefully programmed into the overall site activities.

FIGURE 7 - DETAIL OF PAD FOOTING (1:100)

FIGURE 8 - RETAINING WALL DETAIL (1:25)

FIGURE 9 - SLAB/WALL JUNCTION (1:25)

Concrete Level

The piling technique used required the concrete in the piles to be brought up to ground level. This meant that a significant quantity of concrete had to be subsequently cut out to facilitate pile cap construction. Future contracts could consider reducing the overall site level to the underside of the pile cap prior to commencing piling. This would not have been possible everywhere on the Jervis St. site because of the danger of undermining adjacent foundations and also because of programming requirements.

Concrete Setting Time

Careful control of the concrete strength in the female piles is essential to ensure later cutting through by the male piles.

It was hoped that the piles could have been cut down to underside of capping beam within one or two days. However, this did not always prove possible due to the construction of adjacent piles or to other activities on the site. It was found that a period of about seven days was a more realistic figure.

Unstable Ground

At several locations around the site perimeter, e.g. the listed buildings on Upper Abbey St. and near the Quinnsworth facade on Mary St. unstable ground was encountered during the augering process at the top of the weathered rock stratum. The problem occurred when the casing was held up on one side by a block of rock and was overcome by pre-concreting the piles following auger drilling and then drilling through the concrete with the rock drill.

8.3 Excavation

Excavation and construction of the basement and foundations commenced in the centre of the site as the secant piled wall was being constructed. Pierce elected to do this under the restriction that the water level in the gravels around the perimeter of the site did not drop by more than 1m until the secant piling had been completed. A contingency plan involving recharging of the gravels was drawn up. However, this measure was not required in practice. This excavation did not encroach any closer than approximately 10 m to the wall before the piles were installed and a 1,200 mm x 1,000 mm deep capping beam was constructed.

constructed by the piling contractor Murphy International Ltd. The pile lengths varied between 6.5m and 11.9m. The value of the piling contract was approximately £1m.

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FIGURE 7 - DETAIL OF PAD FOOTING (1:100)

FIGURE 8 - RETAINING WALL DETAIL (1:25)

FIGURE 9 - SLAB/WALL JUNCTION (1:25)

The excavation adjacent to the wall was then carried out in two stages. The ground level immediately adjacent to the wall was first reduced by approximately 3 m and for a width of approximately 4 m. Thereafter, the excavation was sloped as a berm at 1 in 1 to formation level.

The temporary props were then installed by excavating "slots" through the berm in front of the wall. Reaction to the load being transferred axially through the temporary props was provided in both base sliding resistance and passive resistance against rock from a prop reaction block. This block consisted essentially of a cubic metre block of concrete constructed below formation level into which the universal column section was embedded. This prop reaction block is illustrated schematically in Figure 5. Every second prop was installed at any one time (i.e. 12m apart), in order to minimise the quantity of soil material removed and hence ensure the support of the secant pile wall. The intermediate props were then installed. The remaining material in front of the wall was then excavated down to formation level.

Some problems associated with this technique were as follows:

- the work was awkward and time consuming,
- the struts had to be kept below the capping beam for structural reasons and to allow insertion of shuttering for the permanent slab,
- the reaction blocks had to be located so as to avoid the drainage system.

8.4 Dewatering

As previously stated the site investigation revealed standing groundwater level to be approximately 3.5 m below ground level at approximately 0.0 mOD. Formation levels were generally between - 2.25 m and - 3.30 mOD with deeper drainage and service trenches. A lowering of the groundwater level within the site was obviously necessary. This was achieved by maintained pumping from sumps at various locations around the site at levels just below the required formation or foundation level.

Groundwater level was successfully maintained at a sufficiently suppressed level through the basement construction period to allow all construction to be completed in the dry.

8.5 Rock Anchorages

As the basement slab is located beneath the ambient ground water level it was necessary to install rock anchorages to provide long term uplift resistance. 443 No. anchorages were installed by Rocklift Ltd. The design of the rock anchorages involved both design of the members themselves and the basement slab / anchor head waterproofing detail.

The anchorages comprise 9m long, 50 mm dia. single bar anchorages and were installed in a 125 mm dia. borehole. The anchorages are positioned on an approximate 2.5m x 2.5m grid where required. The anchorages are double corrosion protected and are designed to sustain a working load of 500kN. This allowed for some loading due to stress relief in the bedrock. Each anchorage was trial stressed successfully to 750 kN.

A detail of the basement slab / anchorage head is shown in Figure 10.

FIGURE 12 PIEZOMETER READINGS IN GRAVEL

FIGURE 13 PIEZOMETER READINGS IN ROCK

9.0 Discussion

9.1 Geology

The ground conditions exposed during excavation were generally as presented in the site investigation report. However, the following points are worth noting:

Due to the pumping operation the gravel layer had become dry. This gravel appeared to have a higher fines content than the approximate 5% suggested by the site investigation grading curves. This enabled them to sustain negative pore pressures. When excavation commenced in the centre of the site, it was possible to cut vertical faces in the 2m layer of gravel while it supported approximately 3m of made ground above. These vertical faces could be maintained for considerable time during the summer construction period despite the trafficking of heavily loaded vehicles. It is thought that the very dry weather during summer 1995 contributed to this process. The stability of the gravels may also have been contributed to locally by the presence of old basements and foundations behind the excavated face.

It was possible to examine in-situ the upper layers of the limestone bedrock, i.e. the weathered rock. The material appeared as cuboidal blocks of strong or very strong limestone interbedded with thin layers of silty clay or mudstone (see Figure 11) or alternatively of cobble and boulder sized

fragments of limestone in a matrix of silty clay.

It was possible to excavate this material with a conventional tracked excavator. In view of this, modelling of this layer as a frictional material was justified.

9.2 Groundwater

Groundwater flow into the excavation was relatively easily controlled by pumping from sumps. The sumps used were usually located in the excavation for a foundation or for drainage pipes. Typically four to six, 100mm dia. to 150mm dia., pumps were in use at any one time. The groundwater was clean and was pumped into the Dublin Corporation system.

The nature of the weathered rock made the intermittent pumping necessary as it was not possible to predict the level of groundwater seepage until an excavated face was exposed.

Piezometric levels in the gravels and in the bedrock were measured at various points around the site during the works. All of the piezometer readings for the instruments in the gravels are shown in Figure 12 and those for the rock are shown in Figure 13. Basement excavation commenced in mid-July 1995 and it was largely completed by the end of October 1995.

A general comment would be that the readings are "spiky" in nature because of the intermittent pumping effort.

With the exception of PZ102, which was located between the secant pile wall and the Marks and Spencer wall, all of the readings for the gravels remained relatively steady.

In general the response of the piezometers in the bedrock was in hydraulic continuity with that in the gravels. The exception is that for piezometers M2, M4 and PZ102, all of which are located at the Mary St. / Liffey St. corner of the site, which show a drop in piezometric level of up to 4m.

This relatively high drop in piezometric level did not have implications for adjacent structures as all are either piled or founded at a higher level on the gravels. Regular inspections of adjacent structures revealed no effects. Such a drop in piezometric level could have implications for buildings founded on timber piles.

9.3 Retaining Wall Movement

Inclinometers were installed in male piles at two location's, adjacent to the Jervis St. Hospital Facade and the Quinnsworth Facade on Mary St., in order to measure lateral wall movement.

FIGURE 14 - INCLINOMETER READINGS

No movement was measured on the Mary St. Facade. The actual versus predicted movements (from FREW) for the Jervis St. Facade are shown on Figure 14. It can be seen that the maximum recorded movement was 3mm compared to about 9mm predicted. FREW accurately predicted the shape of the wall deformation. This over-prediction could be due to over conservative parameters, particularly of the at rest pressures and the soil and wall stiffness' being used in the analysis.

However, it is felt that the surcharge loading due to the facades and the lateral soil pressures assumed by the computer program were not actually being mobilised in reality and that the pressures being imposed on the wall were actually small. It is suggested that the Dublin glacial deposits (including the gravels in this case) have an ability to behave in an undrained manner and stand unsupported, even when loaded, due to a combination of negative excess pore water pressures, cohesion and cementation of the soil grains. This mechanism can be seen in the many high boulder clay cliffs around Dublin and also could be seen on some near vertical temporary excavation faces on the Jervis St. site.

9.4 Ground Movements

Ground movement was monitored at sensitive locations, such as Marks and Spencer. There was no measurable movement recorded.

10.0 Conclusions

10.1 Desk Study

The importance of a simple desk study into the history of a site is illustrated very well in the case of this site by the large underground obstructions, which have implications for pile construction and excavation.

10.2 Geology - Overburden

It would appear that the Dublin Glacial Deposits (including gravels in the right conditions) have an ability to stand unsupported, when excavated, due to negative pore water pressures, cohesion or cementation. This results in lower horizontal earth pressures being mobilised in reality compared to those predicted by conventional soil mechanics (e.g. a drained analysis for the gravels).

10.3 Geology - Weathered Rock

The nature and thickness of the weathered rock can be of significant importance from the point of view of seepage in to excavations and pile construction. Careful examination of this material should be carried out during the site investigation stage.

10.4 Design - Computer Analyses

The use of the computer program FREW was appropriate in the case of the Jervis St. Shopping Centre site, because of the many design case which had to be analysed and the time constraints involved.

However, the program has some limitations, such as, the limited number of prestored finite element analysis stiffness matrices, its inability to compute ground movements and to incorporate easily some recent developments in soil mechanics for example the concept of high stiffness at small strain.

Also because of the availability of cheap and powerful microcomputers it is considered that programs like FREW are

rapidly becoming obsolete and should be replaced by methods such as finite element analyses. The use of these analyses could lead to significant construction cost savings, for example in the wall thickness, the amount of reinforcing, the number of props required etc. However, site investigation will have to be tailored to allow for such analyses.

10.5 Design - Co-operation

In complicated developments, involving many parties, such as Jervis St., good co-operation between client, main contractors, sub - contractors, engineer, temporary works designers, those responsible for instrumentation readings etc. is essential. A program of regular team meeting should be put in place early in the contract.

10.6 Construction - Support System

The installation of the temporary props was a time consuming and exacting process on the Jervis St. site. An alternative means of support, involving horizontal ground anchorages, was considered. However, it was not possible to obtain the necessary wayleaves to install the anchorages beneath adjacent buildings in the time frame available. For future projects the use of ground anchorages should be investigated at an early stage of the project.

Also consideration should be given to utilising adjacent permanent footings to provide reaction at the bottom of the props and thus avoid having to install the concrete reaction blocks.

10.7 Construction - Temporary Props

The use of temporary props at Jervis St. was justified because of the adjacent sensitive structures. However, given the ability of the ground to stand unsupported, as discussed above, the need for temporary props in future developments needs to be questioned carefully.

The omission of temporary props would require careful consideration of many factors, the most important consideration being clearly the safety aspects. Factors such as likely rainfall, adjacent sensitive buildings or services, the presence of water bearing gravels and acceptable movements would also have to be considered.

If all the factors were favourable consideration could be given to omitting the

temporary props and carefully monitoring the performance of the resulting cantilever retaining structure (or the unsupported earth face). If the displacements of the wall or ground exceed certain agreed values a pre-prepared contingency plan could be put into place. This process is called the "observational method" and has been used successfully elsewhere for example in the construction of the Limehouse Tunnel in London Docklands (Blyth, 1994, Ref. 8).

The technique would only apply in Dublin in the very stiff clayey glacial deposits or in dry dense glacial deposits. The presence of water bearing gravels would preclude the technique.

10.8 Ground Anchorages

Where it is possible to design an economic floor slab to span between pads, this system would be preferable to installing rock anchorages.

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